

BOX 2.1 GRID SQUARES AND DEFINITIONS

The traditional recording unit in British and Irish national atlases of flora and fauna is a square measuring 10 km × 10 km, commonly referred to as a '10-km square'. Similarly, a '1-km square' measures 1 km × 1 km, a '20-km square' measures 20 km × 20 km, etc. Those terms are used in this atlas and also 2 km × 2 km squares are described as 'tetrads'. The term 'tetrad' refers to the fact that the square is made up of four 1 km × 1 km squares ('monads'). Similarly, a 10-km square is a 'hectad' (100 monads) and a 100-km square a 'myriad' (10,000 monads), with a 50-km square being a 'quarter myriad'; but these other technical terms are rarely used and are avoided here.

The identification of 100-km squares, 10-km squares and tetrads follows common usage. These, and new notation for 20-km and 50-km squares, are detailed below and illustrated in the figures:

- **100-km square:** in Britain a two-letter prefix applies to all grid references; in Ireland a single-letter prefix, to which a leading 'I' was added to facilitate data processing;
- **50-km square:** the prefix letters of the 100-km square followed by the ordinal compass direction (NE, NW, SE, SW) to identify a quadrant of 25 10-km squares, e.g. SPNE;
- **20-km square:** the prefix letters of the 100-km square followed by a single letter from the DINTY grid (see below) to identify the array of four 10-km squares, e.g. SP_G;
- **10-km square:** the prefix letters of the 100-km square followed by the easting and northing of the southwest corner of the 10-km square, e.g. SP11;
- **Tetrad:** the reference of the 10-km square plus a suffix letter (A–Z, omitting O) describing the location of the tetrad of four 1-km squares, e.g. SP11S. The arrangement of tetrad letters is often colloquially known as the 'DINTY grid' on account of the letters of the second horizontal row.

